

WOMEN'S EDUCATION IN "NEW UZBEKISTAN"

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Abstract: In this article, the attention paid to the education of young women and girls in Uzbekistan today, the essence of the work carried out to support women in all aspects, as well as the important points defined in this regard in the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" tasks mentioned. The article also emphasized the importance of the role of our young scientists in the implementation of the "Third Renaissance" in our country.

Keywords: Action strategy, "New Uzbekistan-Development strategy", "Third renaissance", modern educational programs, artificial intelligence, STEM, science development, scientific outlook.

Аннотация: В данной статье уделено внимание вопросам воспитания молодых женщин и девушек в Узбекистане сегодня, сути проводимой работы по поддержке женщин во всех аспектах, а также важные моменты, определённые в связи с этим в «Стратегии развития Новой Узбекистан». В статье также подчёркнута важность роли наших молодых учёных в осуществлении «Третьего Возрождения» в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: Стратегия действий, «Новый Узбекистан - Стратегия развития», «Третий ренессанс», современные образовательные программы, искусственный интеллект, STEM, развитие науки, научное мировоззрение.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda O'zbekistonda yosh ayol-qizlar ta'limiga qaratilayotgan e'tibor, xotin-qizlarni har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlash borasida olib borilayotgan ishlarning mazmun-mohiyati xamda "Yangi

O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi"da bu borada belgilab olingan muhim vazifalar haqida keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek, mamlakatimizda "Uchunchi renessans"ni amalga oshirishda yosh olimlar ayol-qizlarimizning o'rni juda muhimligiga ham maqolada alohida to'xtab o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Harakatlar strategiyasi, "Yangi O'zbekiston-Taraqqiyot strategiyasi", "Uchunchi renessans", zamonaviy ta'lim dasturlari, suniy intellekt, STEM, ilm-fan taraqqiyoti, ilmiy dunyoqarash.

Today, in Uzbekistan, wide opportunities are being created to support women in every way, to further strengthen their position in society. In particular, this issue is emphasized in the "Strategy of Development" adopted for the development of our country. We can say that the adopted "Strategy of Development" is a logical continuation of the action strategy for 2017-2021 and is one of the most important steps towards further democratization, transparency, openness and establishment of the defined "New Uzbekistan". In the establishment of "New Uzbekistan", special attention is paid to the education system, and the implementation of the important principle "New Uzbekistan begins at the school threshold"¹ is given special importance in this regard and is being implemented. In particular, the quality of education of young girls and women is also very important. Because today the issues of women's education, freedom and gender equality are gaining urgent importance all over the world, which is no secret to anyone.

We support women who want to study at all levels of the education system and create conditions for them,"- said our president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. The adoption of the Women's Education Support Program for 2022-2026 is also very gratifying. Within the framework of the program, it is planned to establish a separate university in the field of textiles on the basis of public-private partnership for the education of mainly women, and to open its technical schools in the coming

¹Mirziyoyev.Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous democratic country of Uzbekistan. -Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan" NMUI, 2016. P-56.

months. Also, the issue of increasing the percentage of female students from the current 24% to 40% in higher education institutions in the fields of specific sciences, technology and law, where the percentage of women is low, is defined as an important task². For this purpose, at least 50% of the quota for female students will be earmarked for specific sciences, technical and legal fields. Starting from the 2022 academic year, for the first time, interest-free loans for a period of 7 years have been introduced for girls studying in universities, technical schools and colleges to pay for educational contracts.

A number of other wide opportunities for women in the education system:

- 1- Starting from the 2022 academic year, the contract money of the girls studying at the master's degree was fully covered from the budget (200 billion soums for 23 thousand girls);
- 2- Every year 50 girls are sent to prestigious foreign universities for bachelor's degree and 10 for master's degree;
- 3- The educational contract of 150 girls (2.1 thousand in total) who have lost their father or mother, needy family representatives in each region will be paid from the local budget;
- 4- Distance learning conditions were created for students with young children;
- 5- A target quota of at least 300 was allocated annually for women in the field of doctoral studies.

In our country, complex and systematic work is being carried out in order to support women in every way, to further increase their influence in society. For example, if we refer to the statistics of previous years, we can mention the following separately:

- 6- In 2021, 2 trillion soums of loans and subsidies were allocated to more than 200,000 projects within the framework of women's entrepreneurship programs, and 320,000 women got permanent jobs;

² «On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026», Development Strategy Centre, Tashkent-2022. P-106.

- 7- In 2021, 190,000 women were trained in professions;
- 8- About 900,000 women were provided socio-economic, medical, legal and psychological support within the framework of the "Women's Register" system launched in 2020;
- 9- In 2021 alone, more than 4,000 women were allocated funds for the initial housing payment;
- 10- 2,000 girls were admitted to universities on the basis of a separate grant, contracts were paid for another 1,800. As a result, in 2021, 60 percent of students entering universities were women (in 2016, this figure was 38 percent);
- 11- In 2021, 1,153 women underwent high-tech medical operations free of charge.

In addition, 5 laws and 55 by-laws on youth policy were adopted in 2016-2021 in Uzbekistan in order to create New Uzbekistan - new opportunities for young people³. This was also a very happy event for the development of our country, especially for us young people.

Today, in our country, all conditions are being created for girls to improve their health, get a full education, get a profession they are interested in, realize their abilities, and engage in entrepreneurial activities. In particular, in the field of health care, consistent measures are being taken to ensure healthy growth of girls from childhood, to increase their medical literacy. We have mentioned above that special attention is paid to all-round support of girls in the field of education, and special additional admission quotas have been introduced for them in higher educational institutions, and interest-free loans have been introduced. In order to further support the education of young women and girls in our country, the Elevate educational program for teaching artificial intelligence technology has also been developed. Women and girls aged 22 and over can take part in it. Google Cloud, together with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, is launching Elevate, a large-scale free training program for women in artificial intelligence technologies. The main goal

³ Law of the republic of Uzbekistan on state policy regarding youth. Law No. ZRU-406. 15.09.2016 <https://lex.uz>

and mission of the program is to increase the opportunities for women to build and continue careers in artificial intelligence technologies by reducing the gender gap in STEM fields consists of.

In conclusion, I can say that we will achieve our noble intention of raising our new Uzbekistan to the stage of high development by educating young people who think fresh and independently, who love their Motherland more than their souls, who will faithfully serve for its bright. Through this, the foundations for a new renaissance in Uzbekistan - the Third Renaissance - will be further strengthened.

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